

Housing, Sanitation Conditions and Housing Amenities in Anoopgarh Village (Jind District), Haryana

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Abstract

Housing is very important need of man's life out of three, that's give the salter of human and other animal. Housing is one of traditional areas of concern for public health. It is important for many aspects of healthy and prosper life. The relationship between housing and health is multifaceted. A healthy home to have structure to be hazards, to provide adequate facilities for sleeping personal hygiene, cleanliness, the preparation and storage of food, to be an environment for comfortable relation. It is considered to be most valuable economic asset and is an important indicator of lifestyle and socio economic status of human .after independence we complete 70 years of freedom but majority of people have been deprived of standard housing, basic facilities likes, water sanitation, public hygiene, electricity, toilet facility, and good quality of life. Nayer (1997) "Housing condition, availability of drinking water, sanitation facilities etc. might contribute to the health improvement of the people and determines the quality of life of society"

Ministry of finance (2012), "Government policies are directed are directed toward economic and social up liftmen of these segments to enable to reap the benefits of growth and bring marginalized section of the society into the mainstream". This study indicates that contribution toward housing conditions including sanitary facilities will lead to improvement in the aspect of health.

Key words: housing, household, sanitation, and assets.

Objective:

1. To study the housing and sanitation condition of study area.

2. To study the housing condition of house like layout, structured, living room, cleanliness and ventilation
3. To analysis the basic requirement like, water, electricity and waste disposal management in study area.

Data base:

Present study is based on both the primary and secondary sources of data. Primary data was collected with the help of a structured household schedule which hosts all the necessary questions that are required to understand the social and economic status of a household. The secondary data was collected from various concerned government departments. Revenue department was approached to collect the data about the total area of village and dominant crops sown in different seasons. Data related to the average depth of groundwater level was collected from Groundwater Cell, Jind. Census data for the year 2011 and data related to the existing infrastructure in the village was collected from the office of the District Statistical Officer, Jind. Gram Panchyat office was approached to collect some relevant information needed for the successful execution of field survey. Google earth application is used to acquire the satellite image of the study area.

Research Methodology:

In the process of the collection of data, a census survey was conducted in the study area from 07-09 november 2017 to collect the data of the village. For the purpose, direct personal interview method was adopted where the students made interactions with the heads and other family members of each and every household to fill all the details in the schedule design for the purpose of research. Since, the target group was not very large; that is why, census survey was conducted in the study area.

The parameters used in the study include type of houses, kitchen facility, number of rooms, transport facility, communication, household assets, cooking fuel, toilet construction, toilet facility, water and waste disposal, source of drinking water, electricity and house amenities status. These indicators are studied according to social, economic and occupational status of households. The social characteristics of each household are assessed on the bases of their castes. The caste categories considered are upper casts, middle caste and lower caste. In defining the caste as upper, middle and lower the reservation policy of government of Haryana is followed. The caste categorized as upper are the general caste, middle are the backward castes (B.C.) and lower are the scheduled castes (S.C.). The economic characteristics of each

household are assessed based on the land ownership of a household. The households categorized as landless are who do not own any cultivable land; marginal farmers are the households with a land ownership of up to 2.5 acres; small farmers are those who have a land ownership of 2.5 to 5.0 acres and households with 5.0 to 10 acres land ownership are categorized as medium farmers, households that have land ownership above 10 acres are categorized as large farmers. The occupational characteristics of each household were assessed on occupation. The analysis is done by using percentage method and diagrams. to analysis the data and results apply the tabulation method and show the finding in percentage method. In order to know housing and sanitation conditions of the house of Anoopgarh village community has been classified into three social groups according to caste hierarchy.

1. Upper class
2. Middle class
3. Lower class

Profile of study area:

Anoopgarh is an old village. It is near about 300 years old. This village lies in district Jind state of Haryana. this is situated 12kms. From district headquarter of Jind. the exact location of the village of Anoopgarh is 29.2442 degree North to 76.3608 degree East. Elevation of this village is 226 meters above sea level. The village settlement is compact. The total area is 571 hectares out of which 25 hect. is under Lal Dora.

Social structure: The total population is 2064 person according to the primary survey of 2017. Among them 1102 male and 962 female population. Total number of households were 400. Total cast 10 in this villege. there is all caste belong from hindu religion only. Jaat is the dominate caste at this village. they are living at the topmost are within dora while schedule caste is living in periphery area in south side jaat is the dominant caste at this village. They are living at the topmost area within Dora while schedule caste is living on periphery area in South side. Jaat have more landholding others. Anoopgarh basically a patriarchal society most of the economic social and political system is dominated by man.

Physical structure:

Soil: Mostly alluvial soil found in the Anoopgarh village.

Relief: Basically, this is plain area

Climate factors:

Rainfall: the average rainfall over the village as a whole is 55 cm. over 70% of the annual rainfall is received during the monsoon months of July to September. Some precipitation, constituting about 10 per cent of the annual rainfall, is also received during the winter months of December to February in association with western disturbances which pass across the village or its neighbourhood from west to east, affecting the weather over the village in this season.

Temperature: the mean daily maximum temperature during June is around 41C and the mean daily minimum around 27C.

Humidity 75-80% in the morning and 55-65% in the afternoon.

Water Table: the depth of water table generally ranges from 0.83 to 39.80 meters the water table records a general decline ranging from 0.01 to 2.48 meters during the extreme summer months.

Map of study area:

Discussion and Analysis:

Table no 1. Distribution of structure of house according to social group.

Figures in parentheses are percentage of total

Social group	Kutchha	Semi Pucca	Pucca	Total
Upper class	6(2.16)	171(62.40)	97(34.40)	274(100)
Middle class	3(5.17)	45(77.58)	10(17.24)	58(100)
Lower class	7(12.72)	38(69.09)	10(18.18)	55 (100)

Total	16(4.43)	245(65.63)	117(30.23)	387(100)
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Table shows that the housing types of a community reflect its socio economic condition . it is evident from table 1 that about total semi pucca houses 65.63 % and the proportion of semi pucca houses in middle class group 77.58% lowest among the semi pucca houses in upper class 62.40% .The highest kutcha houses in lower class is 12.72 % and the lowest kutcha houses in upper class is only 2.16 % . Our findings is that the housing type of middle class is good condition more than the lower class in study area.

Table no 2: Distribution of number of room according to Social Group

Social group	0-2 rooms	3-4 rooms	5-6 rooms	Total
Upper class	85 (35.56)	116(48 .53)	38(15 .89)	239 (100)
Middle class	16(14.00)	21(53.84)	02(05.12)	39(100)
Lower class	37(69.81)	15 (28.30)	01(01.88)	53(100)
Total	138(41.69)	152 (45.92)	41(12.38)	311(100)

Table 2 shows that the number of rooms and the living standard of family. The family which have 5-6 rooms shows the high living standard its 12.38 % and highest in upper class that is 15.89%. This is evident the table that about total 3-4 rooms is 45.92 % and the highest ratio in 53.84 % in middle class group. The lowest no of rooms 0-2 is 41.69 % in middle group is 14%

Table no 3: Distribution of kitchen facility according to Social Group

Social group	Open	Separate	Total
Upper class	64 (24.90)	193 (75.09)	257 (100)
Middle class	16(43.24)	21 (56.75)	37 (100)
Lower class	37 (71.15)	15 (28.84)	52 (100)
Total	117 (33.81)	229 (66.18)	346 (100)

In this table shows the kitchen facility in village in good condition. the highest separate kitchen facility from upper class which is 75.09 % and lowest in lower class 28,30 %.

Table no 4: Distribution Of animal space according to Social Group

Social group	With compound	Separate	Total
Upper class	117(50.44)	115(49.56)	232(100)
Middle	17(65.39)	09(34.61)	26(100)
Lower	21(56.75)	16(43.24)	37(100)
Total	155(52.54)	14(47.45)	295(100)

Table no 4 shows that the separate animal space of houses in good condition. The highest separate space in upper class is 49.56 % but with compound ratio is also nearby separate ratio. The lowest separate animal space in middle class is that 34.61%.

Table no 5 Distribution Of housing ventilation according to social group

Social group	Good	Satisfactory	Bad	Total
Upper class	131(49.26)	129(48.49)	06(02.25)	266(100)
Middle	13(35.13)	22(59.45)	02(05.40)	37(100)
Lower	13(22.00)	37(62.71)	09(15.25)	59(100)
Total	157(43.38)	188(51.93)	17(04.69)	362(100)

Table no 6 Distribution Of cleanliness level of house according to social group

Social group	Good	Satisfactory	Bad	Total
Upper class	111(56.92)	80(41.03)	04(02.25)	195(100)
Middle	14(23.52)	13(76.47)	00(00.00)	17(100)
Lower	11(34.37)	17(53.12)	04(12.50)	32(100)
Total	126(51.63)	110(45.08)	08(03.57)	244(100)

Table no 5 shows the housing ventilation condition that is highest good in upper class 49.26% and lowest in lower class that is 22%. The bad ventilation condition is lowest in upper class is only 2.25 % and highest in lower class that is 15.25%. In table no 6 finding is that the cleanliness level of housing are highest good in upper class is 56.92% and lowest good in middle class is 23.52% and bad cleanliness condition is in upper class 2.25% and highest in lower class that is 12.50%. There is no bad condition is in middle class it is satisfactory condition of housing.

Table no.7 Distribution Of toilet facility in the house according to social group

Social group	Yes	No	Total
Upper class	230 (77.70)	66(22.29)	296(100)

Middle	36(85.17)	06(14.28)	42(100)
Lower	57(93.44)	04(06.55)	61(100)
Total	323(80.95)	76(19.04)	399(100)

Table no. 8 Distribution. Of types of toilet in the house according to social group

Social group	Dry	Flush	Total
Upper class	59(24.43)	204(77.56)	263(100)
Middle	48(68.57)	22(31.42)	70(100)
Lower	29(43.28)	38(56.71)	67(100)
Total	136(34.00)	264(66.00)	400(100)

Table no. 9: Distribution Of toilet construction in the house according to social group

Social group	Toilet scheme construction (TSC)	Self-construction	Total
Upper class	23(08.82)	238(91.18)	261(100)
Middle	09(23.68)	29(76.32)	38(100)
Lower	14(23.72)	45(76.28)	59(100)
Total	46(12.84)	312(87.16)	358(100)

Table no 7 shows that 80.95 % household have toilet facility and the proportion of that facility higher among lower class is 93.44 % where upper class have 78% toilet facility in the study area and in middle class have 85.17 %. Table no 8 shows that about 80 %household have own toilet. The ratio of flush toilet is 66 % and that is good condition in study area. There is a higher gap between dry and flush toilet and the dry toilet is highest in middle group have 68.57% and flush facilities is highest in 77.56 %. Table no 9 shows that most of toilet have built by self and which is about 87.16% .The proportion of self-built up in upper class that is 91.18 % and highest built up in T.S.C. Scheme is in lower class that is 23.72%.

Table no. 10 Distribution. Of solid waste disposal according to social group

Social Group	Open	Other	Total
Upper class	265 (98.91)	04(01.49)	269(100)

Middle	56(90.33)	06(09.67)	62(100)
Lower	82(98.80)	01(01.20)	83(1000)
Total	403(97.35)	11(02.65)	399(100)

Table no 10 shows that the waste disposal mechanism is an indicator of level of cleanliness of housing and settlement. All of household in village expect one throw the solid and semi-solid waste in the open . The open disposal is highest in all class that is upper, middle and lower class respectively 98%, 90% and 98% so our finding is that there is no management of waste disposal and that effect the health of people of study area.

Table no.11: Ownership pattern of vehicles according to Social Group

Social group	Car	Scooter	Jeep	Cycle	Total
Upper class	39(12.66)	157(50.97)	08(02.60)	104(33.76)	308(100)
Middle	02(05.00)	13(32.50)	00(00)	25(62.50)	40(100)
Lower	04(08.16)	21(42.85)	00(00)	24(48.90)	49(100)
Total	45(11.33)	191(48.10)	08(02.00)	153(38.50)	397(100)

Table no 11: Shows that transport is the movement of animal, human, and goods from one place to another place. Its role is important in economic development. The availability of cycle is high in middle class that is 62.50%. The availability of car is highest in upper class is 12.66% comparatively other classes and jeep vehicles in only find in upper class is 2.60% .The scooter availability is highest in upper class is 50.97% .

Table no .12: Distribution Of communication according to Social Group

Social group	Phone	Computer	Internet	Total
Upper class	241 (77.00)	26(08.30)	46(14.60)	313(100)
Middle	38(77.50)	05(10.00)	06(12.20)	49(100)
Lower	58(93.50)	01(01.60)	03(04.80)	62(100)
Total	337(72.20)	36(07.50)	55.(12.20)	424(100)

Table no 12 shows that it seems that diffusion of mobile phone has taken place very fast in the village. It shows that about 80% household in the village own mobile phone. However the

proportion of mobile phone owning household is relatively high among lower class (93%) and upper class (77%). However the ratio of computer and internet relatively less used by middle class (5% and 6%) and (17% and 3%) schedule caste.

Table no. 13: Distribution Of ownership of assets according to Social Group

Social group	Open	covered	Total
Upper class	179(73.60)	64(18.60)	243(100)
Middle	49(92.40)	04(08.10)	53(100)
Lower	12(54.50)	10(45.40)	22(100)
Total	240(75.40)	78(24.50)	318(100)

Table No. 13 show that fridge is a very common household assists in the village. About (50%) household in the village have fridge. The proportion of fridge owning household is highest among upper class (52%) and lowest among middle class (39%). About (36%) household also own television about (40%) household have own T.V. the availability of T.V. is comparatively less among lower class (20%). About (20%) other assets have found in the village which is very low proportion.

Table no .14 Distribution of waste water disposal according to Social Group

Social group	Open	Covered	Total
Upper class	179(73.60)	64(18.60)	243(100)
Middle	49(92.40)	04(08.10)	53(100)
Lower	12(54.50)	10(45.40)	22(100)
Total	240(75.40)	78(24.50)	318(100)

Table No. 14 show that waste water disposal mechanism is an indicator of level of cleanliness of house and settlement. This table show that 76 per cent house have open waste water disposal and 24 percent house of village used covered waste water disposal. There show that almost house of village used open waste water disposal.

Table no 15 Distribution of drinking water service according to social group.

Social group	Tap	Hand pump	Well	Tank	Total
Upper class	111(38.40)	148(51.20)	01(0.3)	29(10)	289(100)
Middle	32(59.20)	19(35.18)	00(00)	03(3)	54(100)
Lower	40(64.50)	19(30.60)	00(00)	03(4.80)	62(100)

Total	183(45.18)	186(45.90)	01(00.20)	35(8.60)	405(100)
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Table No. 15: Show that availability of drinking water is a crucial component of public health. Water treated at the water work and supply through pipeline is considered safe for human consumption. This table shows that 45 percent of houses in village have tap water supply. The proportion of such houses is very high in lower class 65 percent, the dependant on hand pump, well is particularly high among upper class 51 percent and middle class 32 percent. 8.06 percent of houses in village use tanks service.

Table no 16 Distribution of light source according to social group.

Social group	Electricity	Other	Total
Upper class	271 (100)	00(00)	271(100)
Middle	39(100)	00(00)	39(100)
Lower	60(100)	00(00)	60(100)
Total	370(100)	00(000)	370(100)

Table No. 16: This table shows that 100 percent of houses in village have electricity connecting. The level of electricity is 100 percent in all caste. In fact many electric connections in village are good. It was difficult to distinguish between legal and illegal connections in many cases. All the caste has inverter facilities.

Table no.17: Distribution of alternate light source according to Social Group

Social group	Inverter	Solar	generator	Total
Upper class	222(100)	00	00	222(100)
Middle	34(100)	00	00	34(100)
Lower	30(100)	00	00	30(100)
Total	286(100)	00	00	286(100)

Table No. 17: This table shows that 100 percent of houses in village have Inverter connecting. The level of Inverter is 100 percent in all caste. In fact many electric connections in village are good. All the caste has inverter facilities.

Table no.18 Distribution of cooking fuel according to social group

Social group	Wood	L.P.G	Electricity	Solar	Total
Upper class	227(50.10)	226(49.80)	00	00	453(100)
Middle	43(42.10)	59(57.80)	01(0.98)	00	102(100)
Lower	55(51.40)	52(48.60)	00	00	107(100)
total	325(49.10)	337(50.90)	00	00	661(100)

Table no.18 shows that 51%house of village used L.P.G for cooking and 49.57% house of middle class used most L.P.G 49% house of village used wood for cooking food. it the wood source lower class used most 52%house for cooking nut L.P.G is not used for regularly for cooking in most households.

Conclusion:

It is evident from the preceding discussion that layout pattern and structure of the houses is changing in village in Anoopgarh. The proportion of semi pacca houses in backward caste groups 78% lowest among the semi pacca houses upper caste 63%. The highest kucha houses schedule caste 13%. The lowest kutchha houses in upper caste in 2%. We can say that he housing types of backward caste is good conditions more than the lower class in Anoopgardh village. The number of rooms show that the living standard of family. The family which have 5-6 rooms shows the high living standard. This is evident the table that about total 3-4 rooms 46%. The highest 3-4 rooms conditions backward caste 54%. The lowest conditions in this rooms schedule caste 29%. The highest 5-6 rooms conditions upper caste 16%. The lowest conditions in this rooms schedule caste 2%. The ventilation of the houses is related to condition of the human health. The highest ventilation conditions of the houses upper caste 50%. The lowest ventilation condition of the houses schedule caste 22%. The total bad ventilation condition of the houses in Anoopgarh village was 5%. The highest bad ventilation condition in case of upper caste was 2%. The lowest bad ventilation condition in schedule caste was 15%. We can show that the ventilation condition of upper caste is good than the schedule caste in Anoopgarh village. The level of cleanliness is a big factor in housing condition. The level of cleanliness is bad in percentage house in the village. The proportion of such house is very among. The schedule caste 12% and low among backward that is zero. On the other hand 52% houses in the village have better cleanliness level. The proportion of such house is 57% in case of upper

caste. About 45% houses have satisfactory cleanliness condition and there is not a significant difference in this regard across the caste groups.

It also refers to the maintenance of hygienic condition through services such as garbage collection. The importance of hygienic toilet lies in an effort to prevent diseases which can be transmitted through human waste. 80% households have toilet facility and the proportion of that facility is higher among schedule caste 94%. Where upper caste has 78% and backward cast have 86% and 20% house do not have toilet facilities at all. About 80% households have own toilet. There is a higher gap between dry and flush and proportion of flush which is about 66% is higher than dry. Dry's proportion is 34%. The most toilet have built by self. Which is about 87% and the proportion of in flush type is higher among upper caste 91% and the same ratio of backward and schedule caste 76%.

The waste disposal mechanism is an indicator of level of cleanliness of house and the settlement. Table show that all the household in village except one throw the solid and semi solid waste in the open. Insect along the entry points in the village there is the stinking smell of waste. The disposal of waste in the open space also affects the ambience of the village.

The transport is the movement of animal, human and goods from one place to another place. It has important role in economic development. The proportion of scooter owning household comparatively high among upper caste was 51%. Cycle is other mode of transport in the village which is also higher percentage about 39% backward caste higher per cent in the ownership of cycle which is 62% where upper caste is 34% and schedule caste is 49%.

Fridge is a very common household assets in the village. About 50% households in the village have fridge. The proportion of fridge owning household is highest among upper caste 52% and lowest among backward caste 39%. About 36% households also own television about 40% households have own T.V. the availability less among schedule caste 20%. The waste water disposal mechanism is an indicator of level of cleanliness of house and settlement. This table show that 76% house have open waste water disposal and 24% house of village used covered waste water disposal. There show that almost house of village used open waste water disposal.

Totally 100% house in village has electricity connecting. The level of electricity is 100% in all caste in fact many electric connections in village are illegal. It was difficult to distinguish between legal and illegal used tanks service.

Total 51% house of village used L.P.G. for cooking and 49.57% house of backward caste used most L.P.G.% house of village used wood for cooking food it is the source of air pollution in the house hardly only 1% house used electricity for cooking. In the wood source schedule caste used most 52% house for cooking but L.P.G. is not used for regulatory for cooking in most house holds.

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